

International Conference on | i
Green Technology and Talent Management

OXFORD

(AFFILIATED WITH POKHARA UNIVERSITY)

COLLEGE OF ENGINEERING & MANAGEMENT

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Book of Abstracts

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International Conference on Green Technology and Talent Management

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Message from the Vice Chancellor

Dear Conference organizing team,

OCEM's International Conference

I want to express my heartfelt gratitude to your esteemed institution for organizing the OCEM's International Conference on Green Technology and Talent Management. Organizing an international conference poses significant challenges in terms of finances, technology, and establishing a network of researchers. In light of these considerations, we commend your commitment to academic excellence and your contribution to the advancement of knowledge. The conference will certainly convene scholars, researchers, and experts from diverse fields, fostering collaboration and stimulating intellectual development. Your endeavors have not only elevated the academic reputation of your college but have also enhanced the stance of our university and contributed to the progress of our nation.

In this critical era, research plays a crucial role, and I am highly influenced by the active engagement OCEM faculty members in research endeavors. Engaging in research is paramount to enhancing the quality of education and propelling the growth of our institution. The knowledge and insights gained through research are fundamental in addressing current challenges and making substantial contributions to our society.

I extend my deepest gratitude to the OCEM Research Management Cell, and the entire organizing team for their outstanding effort and unwavering dedication in organizing this conference. Your commitment to academic excellence and research sets a commendable example, and I am confident that this event will inspire others to pursue similar undertakings.

I eagerly anticipate our ongoing collaboration and the prospect of witnessing further academic accomplishments from your esteemed institution.

Warm regards,

Prof. Dr. Prem Narayan Aryal

Vice Chancellor, Pokhara University

Message from the Principal

I am pleased to welcome you all to the OCEM's International Conference on Green Technology and Talent Management. It is an honor for us to organize this conference, which aims to bring together experts from various fields to share their knowledge, experiences, and ideas.

As the Principal of this institution, I am delighted to see such a positive response from scholars across the country. This conference provides researchers with an opportunity to collaborate and discuss crucial ideas that will contribute to the advancement of knowledge in their respective fields.

The conference theme, "Green Technology and Talent Management," is particularly relevant in today's context, as industries are currently facing challenges in managing talent due to a significant number of young individuals choosing to study abroad, resulting in the brain drain. Moreover, green technology is gaining recognition as a means to reduce environmental pollution. Academics must adopt an interdisciplinary approach to address these complex problems.

I am confident that this conference will serve as a platform for academics to share their work, connect with peers, and learn from the best in their fields. I hope that this conference will inspire attendees to strive for excellence in research and make significant contributions to our society.

I wish everyone a productive and enjoyable experience at the International Conference on Green Technology and Talent Management.

Best wishes,

Prof. Er. Hari Prasad Bhandari

Principal, Oxford College of Engineering and Management

Message from RMC Head

Dear esteemed chief guest, keynote speakers, distinguished guests, special guests, colleagues, presenters, participants, and students

I extend my warmest greetings to each of you as we prepare for the forthcoming OCEM International Conference on Green Technology and Talent Management, scheduled to take place on May 10th and 11th, 2024 at OCEM. It gives me great pleasure to welcome you to this significant event, which serves as a vital platform for the exchange of knowledge, ideas, and experiences in the fields of Green Technology and Talent Management. In today's rapidly changing world, where sustainability and human capital are of paramount importance, our collective efforts to advance research and practices in these areas are more crucial than ever before.

The OCEM Research Department is dedicated to driving innovation and fostering collaboration among researchers, academics, industry experts, and policymakers. Through this conference, we aim to create an inclusive space where diverse perspectives converge to address the complex challenges and opportunities facing our society.

As the head of the research department, I am deeply honored to be part of this endeavor and am excited to witness the contributions that each of you will make towards advancing the leading edge of knowledge and practices. Your participation and engagement are integral parts to the success of our shared mission on our societal changes. I encourage you to seize this opportunity to network, collaborate, and learn from your peers, as we attempt to catalyze positive change and create a sustainable future for the generations to come. On the behalf of the entire OCEM Research Department team, I extend my heartfelt appreciation to all who have contributed to making this conference a reality. Together, let us embark on this journey of discovery, innovation, and impact.

I am overjoyed to welcoming you personally to the OCEM International Conference and to the enriching discussions and interactions that lie ahead.

With warm regards,

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Basanta Prasad Adhikari

RMC Head

Oxford College of Engineering and Management

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Pokhara University
Oxford College of Engineering and Management
Research Management
Gaidakot, Nawalpur, Nepal
International Conference
on
Green Technology and Talent Management
Program Schedule
May 10-11, 2024

Venue: OCEM Auditorium, Gaidakot-2, Nawalparasi

Day- I: 2080/01/28 (May 10, 2024)

Time	Program	Venue
7:00-8:00 Am	Breakfast and registration	Cafeteria
8:00-10:00 Am	Opening session	Main Conference Hall
10:00-11:30 Am	Panel discussion on Green Technology	Main Conference Hall
11:30-12:15 Pm	Keynote Speech –I [Prof. Dr. Thomas Koleher, Research Director, Dresden, German] (30 min speech, 15 min discussion)	Main Conference Hall
12:15-1:15 Pm	Parallel Technical Sessions	Conference Hall-A Conference Hall-B
1:15-2:15 Pm	Lunch	Cafeteria
2:15-6:00 Pm	Site visit and Jungle Safari, Sauraha	
6:30 onward	Dinner and Networking	Cafeteria

Day- II: 2080/01/29 (May 11, 2024)

Time	Program	Venue
7:00-8:00 Am	Breakfast and registration	Cafeteria
8:00-8:30 Am	Keynote Speech –II [Prof. Dr. Moch. Bruri Triyono, Head Department of Vocational and Technology, University of Yogyakarta, Indonesia]	Main Hall
8:30-10:00 Am	Parallel Technical Sessions	Conference Hall-A Conference Hall-B
10:00-10:30Am	Keynote Speech –III [Dr. Ari J. Tervashonka, Researcher on Systematic Analysis and History of Science]	Conference Hall-A Conference Hall-B
10:30-11:45Am	Parallel Technical Sessions	Conference Hall-A Conference Hall-B
11:45-12:45 Pm	Keynote Speech –IV [Assoc. Prof. Dr. Binay Kumar Mishra, School of Engineering Pokhra University] Keynote Speech –V [Assoc. Prof. Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra, Research Professor Kathmandu College of Management, Nepal]	Main Conference Hall
12:45-1:30 Pm	Lunch	Cafeteria
1:30-3:00 Pm	Parallel Technical Sessions	Conference Hall-A Conference Hall-B
3:00-3:30 Pm	Keynote Speech –VI [Amit Shankar, Associate Professor of Marketing, IIM Visakhapatnam]	Main Conference Hall
3:30-5:00 Pm	Panel discussion on Talent Management	Main Conference Hall
5:00-5:30 Pm	Keynote Speech –VII [Assoc. Prof. Dr. Cha-Hsuan Liu, Wittenborg University of Applied Sciences]	Main Conference Hall
5:30-6:00 Pm	Closing Session	Main Conference Hall

Keynote Speech